

Keywords:

#tool, #ethics, #legal, #RDM,
#researchdatamanagement, #compliance,
#EOSCinPractice

Supporting the implementation and adoption of EOSC by helping resource providers verify legal and ethics onboarding requirements.

An EOSC in Practice Story where a free tool is offered to prospective providers to self-assess adherence to EOSC rules of participation.

The project involved

NI4OS-Europe (National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe) is a European Horizon 2020 project funded under Grant Agreement no 857645. The project aims to be a core contributor to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) service portfolio, commit to EOSC governance and ensure inclusiveness on the European level for enabling global Open Science. It focuses on supporting the development and inclusion of the national Open Science Cloud initiatives in 15 Member States and Associated Countries in the EOSC governance.

"Since the EOSC Rules of Participation are aligned with FAIR principles, RoLECT is a very useful roadmap beyond the purpose of onboarding services to EOSC. It can indeed serve all researchers for all those issues related with fairness of resources and data in general"

Marianna Katrakazi, Legal Associate @ATHENA RC; Partner @ NI4OS-Europe

The Users

This EOSC in practice story is mainly addressed to **EOSC resource providers** seeking to verify whether the resources they wish to onboard (service or other) align with the **EOSC rules of participation (RoP)**, focusing on the Legal and Ethics requirements. Secondly, it also helps **researchers and research organisations** in raising awareness on the various aspects of the RoP a resource must comply with, if aiming for EOSC onboarding.

RoLECT service access page

The Challenge

The current version of the EOSC rules of participation report edited by the EOSC Executive Board Rules of Participation (RoP) Working Group (WG) states the standards and conduct required of EOSC participants. The rules themselves are high level in order to be generally applicable and long-lived. However, the lack of details and specific compliance criteria can make it difficult for providers to understand all the needed requirements, if they have no legal background or experience, which is not unusual in many companies, especially SMEs. Moreover, openness, transparency, and inclusiveness are among the key principles that have been defined by RoP. Ensuring these principles can be a particularly demanding task when dealing with legal and ethics aspects. Therefore, **a self-assessment tool, which can help EOSC service providers understand the main priorities of EOSC RoP and the actions they have to undertake to be compliant with the core principles of the RoP, is needed.**

The solution

The solution proposed to address the mentioned challenge is a tool called **RoLECT**.

It is designed to promote compliance and identify non-compliance with EOSC RoP and provides a set of questions that are categorized into three levels of importance (high, medium and low) marked with different symbols.

The questions have been classified according to the priorities set out in EOSC RoP. The symbols serve as indicators of compliance and help resource providers assess what information or omission of information is most important for verifying adherence with RoP.

Questions of **high importance** are critical as they reflect the basic principles of RoP.

Questions of **medium importance** regard information that is consistent with EOSC RoP, while **low importance** questions tackle information with a relatively low impact on the assessment result. If, after the assessment of the tool, the minimum standards and requirements are not met, the provider can verify what issues need to be addressed in order to align with the core principles of EOSC RoP. In addition, the assessment raises awareness about compliance criteria since it helps providers to identify any omissions, i.e. any requirements of EOSC RoP included in RoLECT of which they may be unaware.

The service provider

RoLECT was developed by [Athena Research & Innovation Center](#), whose aim is to build knowledge and devise solutions and technologies for the digital society. The company is one of the **NI4OS** partners and a member of the [EOSC Association](#), which brings together key stakeholders in the European research environment to agree on strategies for the advancement of Open Science and to optimise the conditions for research outcomes, and ultimately, to make the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) a reality.

Why become an EOSC provider?

Becoming an EOSC provider allows sharing resources beyond community boundaries. EOSC is indeed intended to make access to scientific data and other scientific outputs easier and more efficient by federating existing scientific data infrastructures and digital infrastructures for data exploitation that are now spread across disciplines and EU member states.

Providing services and tools to the EOSC portal, allows to:

- » Advertise them on the EOSC Portal and promote their adoption outside traditional user groups, reaching a wider user base
- » Get statistics about access requests and customer feedback
- » Get a free online platform where you can manage service requests, interact with users and provide support to them, and agree the most suitable service levels.
- » Allow users to authenticate with their own credentials to access your services and resources thus facilitating their adoption
- » Contribute to the definition and maintenance of EOSC service provisioning policies and the portfolio roadmap.
- » Join the group of providers that meet EOSC quality standards

RoLECT facilitates providers in establishing a presence on the EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace, as it allows to:

- » save time to make an efficient onboarding process
- » have a useful roadmap for all issues related with fairness of resources and data, given that RoP are aligned with fair principles

Read more about why to become an EOSC Provider [here](#).

RoLECT is available on [NI4OS-Europe service catalogue](#), a regional catalogue through which all the project's services are onboarded to EOSC.

Access the RoLECT assessment tool as guest or authenticated user [here](#).

What the users of the service say

RoLECT is very useful since there are no similar tools that can assist resource providers before the onboarding process" (Librarians).

"RoLECT has been regarded as a useful input on legal matters; it can be leveraged to assess legal aspects related to different resource types" (TF charter Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring).

The impact on society

The tool helps enriching the EOSC ecosystem with new resources, because it encourages resource providers to overcome legal and ethics barriers. It helps also to build trust in the resources available via EOSC and it raises awareness and legal and ethics requirements for FAIR research.

Across disciplines

RoLECT has a guided sequence of questions that are standardised and simplify the existing RoP. Those questions have been formulated in such a way that they are general enough to cover all resources or thematic topics regardless of the discipline. So, it helps provide clear legal and ethics requirements that foster cross disciplinary research, avoiding all those fragmented regulations that may apply only to some specific topics.

Future developments

The development team follows closely any discussion and progress on EOSC RoP. The assessment tool will be enriched based on the outputs of EOSC RoP Compliance Monitoring Task Force.

Sustainability for an EOSC in practice

NI4OS-Europe's aspiration is that this resource and the others being developed by the project will be part of a helpful toolkit for all EOSC providers even after the project's end. One important aspect related to making the resources sustainable is the fact that NI4OS-Europe offers all its tools as open source solutions available through GitHub, so that they can be taken up by the communities that are interested in using and further developing the tools

Future funding model scenarios

RoLECT directly addresses one of the major open issues for the EOSC Association, thus for the sustainability of the tool the discussions and outcomes of the EOSC RoP Compliance Monitoring Task Force are monitored closely. The detailed RoLECT sustainability and funding model will be released in the beginning of 2023.

Useful material related to this story

- » [RoLECT presentation at EOSC Symposium 2021](#)
- » [\(Re\)watch the EOSC provider days](#)
- » [Open Science Fair Demo](#)

Want to learn more about the other services being developed by **NI4OS-Europe**? Read [here](#).

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